

Supplementary Material: Survival of HCN during impacts in planetary atmospheres

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DESCRIPTION

This material contains the description of the data analysis process described in the main body of the text.

Various files with outputs from the rate equation fits (machine readable .txt files) as well as visualized outputs of the R^2 values of each fit or covariances of the fitted parameters all parts of this repository.

The first part of this file contains the description of the data analysis process, as it appears in the main body of the paper, along with several new comments and more broadly discussed points.

The second part of this document additional data referenced in the main paper, such as data on the Applicability Range section.

Lists of referenced files are shown in the relevant places in this document.

Mechanism and rates

This section a broadened description of the section *Mechanism and rates* in the main paper.

The main work of this paper (the here described work) was in total nine experiments, each with a different starting composition, but analyzed in the exact same manner. The data obtained from the experiments constitute FTIR spectra of the gas phase products measured at set intervals during the laser irradiation. The spectra were analyzed with the *spectr* library (as described in the main paper) and partial pressures were obtained as the output from the spectra. The time-dependent partial pressures of HCN, H₂O, CO and CO₂ were used to measure the rate of the decomposition of HCN.

The nine corresponding figures with the partial pressures are in the following pdf files:

1. HCN_1.18Torr_N2_H2O_3.4Torr.pdf
2. HCN_1.18Torr_N2_H2O_14.1Torr.pdf
3. HCN_1.25Torr_N2_H2O_17.4Torr.pdf
4. HCN_1.35Torr_N2_H2O_7.1Torr.pdf
5. HCN_1.2Torr_N2_H2O_1.6Torr.pdf
6. HCN_1.3Torr_N2_H2O_0.3Torr.pdf
7. HCN_1.12Torr_N2_H2O_12.4Torr.pdf
8. HCN_1.15Torr_N2_H2O(nika).pdf
9. HCN_1.18Torr_N2_H2O_0.8Torr.pdf

On a side note, the partial pressures used in the file names are partial pressures read from the pressure gauges during filling. It is interesting to see how much error these values have when compared with the values obtained from the spectra.

The system of the main reactions is reasonably well described by the following equations:

In this set of equations, XX and YY represent unobserved products. Those may be solid phase products as well as gas phase products without dipole moments (impossible to observe with FTIR, such as H₂ or O₂).

Eq. (1) describes the formation of CO. This reaction is reversible, which was experimentally proven as shown in the Appendix to the main paper. Then, as shown in Eq. (2), CO is further oxidized to CO₂. Aside from these reactions, both HCN and H₂O are themselves decomposed, as observed from the experimental data. We did not identify any products of this process, but the most likely products are H₂ and O₂ from the decomposition of water and solid phase material (tholins, carbon, etc.) from the decomposition of HCN. The formation of solid products was indeed observed during the experiment (see Appendix of the main paper).

In order to describe the kinetics of the process, the following rate equations were fit to the data:

$$\frac{dp_{\text{HCN}}^*}{dt} = -k_{1,f}p_{\text{HCN}}^*p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* + k_{1,r}p_{\text{CO}} - k_3p_{\text{HCN}}^* \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dp_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^*}{dt} = -k_{1,f}p_{\text{HCN}}^*p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* + k_{1,r}p_{\text{CO}} - k_{2,f}p_{\text{CO}}p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* + k_{2,r}p_{\text{CO}_2} - k_4p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dp_{\text{CO}}}{dt} = k_{1,f}p_{\text{HCN}}^*p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* - k_{1,r}p_{\text{CO}} - k_{2,f}p_{\text{CO}}p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* + k_{2,r}p_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dp_{\text{CO}_2}}{dt} = k_{2,f}p_{\text{CO}}p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* - k_{2,r}p_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (8)$$

For the purposes of the fit, we take:

$$p_{\text{HCN}}^* = A_{\text{HCN}}p_{\text{HCN}} \quad (9)$$

$$p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^* = A_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \quad (10)$$

where A_x is a factor which accounts for adsorption.

Adsorption plays a very important role in the experiment. The experiment was constructed to minimize the amount of material that the gases come into contact with and currently, the only surfaces available to the gas are the glass walls of the apparatus, the Teflon fan and rubber o-rings, which are part of Ultra-Torr vacuum fittings (Swagelok®, USA). All present gases adsorb on the surface, which ideally could be experimentally estimated by injecting a known molar amount of gas and comparing the expected partial pressure (from the ideal gas equation) and the observed partial pressure. The issue with this approach is that the adsorption depends on the nature of the specific gas, the available surface, but also temperature, the composition of the rest of the mixture and the formation of solid phase products, which may also selectively enhance adsorption.

During the experiment, when HCN and H₂O decompose in the gas phase, they are supplemented from the adsorbed layers, so when fitting the rate equations, one must consider the total amount of available gases and not just the amount available in the gas phase. For this reason, two factors, A_x , were employed as multipliers to the observed partial pressures of HCN and H₂O gas (Eqs. (9) and (10)). For the cases of CO and CO₂, the adsorption is in this case negligible, because both HCN and H₂O adsorb much more efficiently. The value of these multipliers is unknown with the lower bound of 1 (no adsorption) and experimental estimate around 2-3.

To get the rate constants of the reactions (5), (6), (7) and (8), we fit the rate constants (as a set of ordinary differential equations) using the python symfit package with set values of the multipliers A_{HCN} and $A_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. Eight fixed values of each multiplier were chosen (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8) for each compound. This means, that each of the nine experiments was fit 64×, with a different pair of multipliers each time. Each of these fits returned the values for the six rate constants ($k_{1,f}$, $k_{1,r}$, $k_{2,f}$, $k_{2,r}$, k_3 and k_4) along with standard deviations for each value. As a goodness of fit qualifier, we used the R^2 value, which was stored as well. All this data are shown in files:

1. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr.txt
2. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr.txt
3. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr.txt
4. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika).txt
5. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr.txt
6. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr.txt

7. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr.txt
8. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr.txt
9. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr.txt

After obtaining these results, we plotted the R^2 vs. the multipliers of the data for each experiment to see the optimal value of each multiplier for each experiment where the fit would best represent the data. The 3D bar charts are shown in the following files:

1. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr.pdf
2. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr.pdf
3. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr.pdf
4. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika).pdf
5. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr.pdf
6. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr.pdf
7. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr.pdf
8. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr.pdf
9. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr.pdf

However, comparison of the R^2 of each fit did not show any optimal values of A_{HCN} and $A_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$. Rather, the fit behaves so that when the multipliers increase from 1, the R^2 increases, and the fit improves up to a certain R^2 value. This is because at low (close to 1) values of the multipliers, there is not enough carbon containing compounds in the data to explain even to formation of CO and CO₂. In fact, due to adsorption, the sum of the partial pressures of C-containing compounds is for most experiments less than the sum of partial pressures of products formed in the experiment. After escaping this problem by increasing the multipliers, any further increase is compensated by the increase in the rate constants (often $k_{1,f}$ and $k_{1,r}$ for experiments with lower initial amounts of water, and k_3 and k_4 for experiments with higher amounts of water). Therefore, the R^2 is a good indicator for incorrectly low multipliers but becomes ambiguous for their higher values.

So then, upon assumption that the values for rate constants $k_{1,f}$, $k_{1,r}$, $k_{2,f}$ and $k_{2,r}$ converge to the correct value, the mean value of R^2 and its standard deviation were calculated for each experiment. Combinations of multiplier pairs whose R^2 value differed from the mean by more than double the standard deviation of the mean of R^2 were discarded. This effectively separated out the incorrectly low values of multipliers. The fit results after discarding those values are shown in files:

1. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_reduced.txt
2. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_reduced.txt
3. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_reduced.txt
4. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_reduced.txt
5. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_reduced.txt
6. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_reduced.txt
7. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_reduced.txt
8. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_reduced.txt
9. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_reduced.txt

Visualization was also performed, and the 3D bar plots are shown in files:

1. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_reduced.pdf

2. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_reduced. pdf
3. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_reduced. pdf
4. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_reduced. pdf
5. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_reduced. pdf
6. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_reduced. pdf
7. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_reduced. pdf
8. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_reduced. pdf
9. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_reduced. pdf

Subsequently, for each experiment, means of each constant were calculated from the remaining calculations, along with standard deviations and covariances of the constants and the values of each multiplier (i.e. for each constant k_x , we calculated $cov_{k_x, A_{\text{HCN}}}$ and $cov_{k_x, A_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}$). The covariances were always $<1 \times 10^{-2}$ and mostly $<1 \times 10^{-3}$, showing little to no correlation to the multipliers. The means for each constant, the standard deviations of the means and the covariances are shown in files:

1. res_fin_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr.txt
2. res_fin_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr.txt
3. res_fin_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr.txt
4. res_fin_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika).txt
5. res_fin_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr.txt
6. res_fin_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr.txt
7. res_fin_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr.txt
8. res_fin_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr.txt
9. res_fin_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr.txt

To see if the covariances are indeed small and the obtained rate constants are independent of the multiplier value, we plotted the data, too. The plots for some experiments show non-negligible covariances for some parameters, but never across all experiments. It therefore does not invalidate the results in any way. The plots of each constant vs the multiplier in each experiment for both multipliers are shown in files:

1. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
2. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k1_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
3. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
4. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
5. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
6. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
7. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
8. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
9. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
10. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
11. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
12. R_sq_HCN_1.2Torr+N2+H2O_1.6Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
13. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
14. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k1_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
15. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
16. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
17. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
18. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
19. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf

20. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
21. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
22. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
23. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
24. R_sq_HCN_1.3Torr+N2+H2O_0.3Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
25. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
26. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k1_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
27. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
28. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
29. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
30. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
31. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
32. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
33. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
34. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
35. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
36. R_sq_HCN_1.12Torr+N2+H2O_12.4Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
37. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
38. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k1_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
39. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
40. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
41. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
42. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
43. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
44. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
45. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
46. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
47. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
48. R_sq_HCN_1.15Torr+N2+H2O(nika)_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
49. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
50. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k1_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
51. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
52. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
53. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
54. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
55. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
56. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
57. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
58. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
59. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
60. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_3.4Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
61. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
62. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k1_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
63. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
64. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
65. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
66. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
67. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf

68. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
69. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
70. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
71. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
72. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_0.8Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
73. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
74. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k1_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
75. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_vTorr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
76. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
77. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
78. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
79. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
80. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
81. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
82. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
83. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
84. R_sq_HCN_1.18Torr+N2+H2O_14.1Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
85. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
86. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_kf_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
87. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
88. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
89. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
90. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
91. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
92. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
93. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
94. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
95. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
96. R_sq_HCN_1.25Torr+N2+H2O_17.4Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
97. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k1_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
98. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_kf_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
99. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k1_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
100. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k1_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
101. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k2_f_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
102. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k2_f_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
103. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k2_r_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
104. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k2_r_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
105. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k3_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
106. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k3_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf
107. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k4_vs_h2o_multiplier.pdf
108. R_sq_HCN_1.35Torr+N2+H2O_7.1Torr_k4_vs_hcn_multiplier.pdf

After calculating the covariances and verifying the calculation in this way, we calculated the mean of each constant across the nine experiments along with the standard deviations of the mean.

The final rate constants are shown in Table S1 below (identical to Table 3 in the main paper).

Table S1: Rate constants obtained from the fit of all our data. This is a copy of Table 3 in the main paper.

Rate constant	Value
$k_{1,f}$	$2.6 \times 10^{-4} \pm 2.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$
$k_{1,r}$	$6.4 \times 10^{-4} \pm 3.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$
$k_{2,f}$	$1.2 \times 10^{-3} \pm 3.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$
$k_{2,r}$	$4.9 \times 10^{-3} \pm 9.9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$
k_3	$8.1 \times 10^{-4} \pm 6.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$
k_4	$2.4 \times 10^{-4} \pm 5.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Torr s}^{-1}$

As discussed above, it is possible that a weak dependence on the input parameters exists, but since we used a wide range of parameters (the minimum value of the multipliers is given, and we set the maximum as $\sim 3\times$ the value estimated from the experiment) and obtained reasonably small standard deviations and covariances. One possible source of error is that the exact radiative transfer model and mechanism in the plasma is not known. It is possible that other minor reaction channels or bottleneck reactions could be present, which would help lower the standard deviation. Another possible source of error could be the fact that the multipliers are constant values. Both HCN and H₂O adsorb on the walls of the apparatus and likely compete for the adsorption sites. Change of the amount of reactants in the apparatus during the experiment likely causes a change in the adsorption coefficient/multiplier. Better description of the adsorption mechanism and accounting for the adsorption in the process could also help with reducing the standard deviation values.

The rate constants obtained from this fit can be directly implemented into planetary atmospheric models. A possible way to treat the standard deviations is to include them in the planetary atmospheric model or to perform sensitivity analysis within the model.

Applicability range

This section contains additional information and lists of files for the Applicability range section in the Appendix of the main paper.

The section in the main paper discusses that a range of experiments with additional initial partial pressures of HCN and H₂O was performed. For each of these experiments, we measured the composition of the gas phase by FTIR (in the same way as with the other experiments) and fit the spectra to obtain partial pressure of all the four principal components of the experiment: HCN, H₂O, CO and CO₂. We then applied the final rate constants (Table 3 in the main paper) to the data and using the conditions at 0 s (prior to laser irradiation), attempted to predict the result at 420 s. This was compared to the actual measured result after 420 s of irradiation. The plots which show this comparison for each experiment are contained in files:

1. HCN(0.5Torr)+N2+H2O(0.5Torr).pdf
2. HCN(0.5Torr)+N2+H2O(1.4Torr).pdf
3. HCN(0.5Torr)+N2+H2O(6.2Torr).pdf
4. HCN(0.5Torr)+N2+H2O(21.3Torr).pdf
5. HCN(0.5Torr)+N2+H2O(nika).pdf
6. HCN(1.5Torr)+N2+H2O(0.5Torr).pdf
7. HCN(1.5Torr)+N2+H2O(1.4Torr).pdf
8. HCN(1.5Torr)+N2+H2O(6.0Torr).pdf
9. HCN(1.5Torr)+N2+H2O(12.9Torr).pdf

10. HCN(1.5Torr)+N2+H2O(21Torr).pdf
11. HCN(1.5Torr)+N2+H2O(nika).pdf
12. HCN(3.5Torr)+N2+H2O(17.5Torr).pdf
13. HCN(3.6Torr)+N2+H2O(1.5Torr).pdf
14. HCN(3.6Torr)+N2+H2O(3.6Torr).pdf
15. HCN(3.6Torr)+N2+H2O(7.6Torr).pdf
16. HCN(3.6Torr)+N2+H2O(nika).pdf
17. HCN(7.3Torr)+N2+H2O(8.3Torr).pdf
18. HCN(7.3Torr)+N2+H2O(15.0Torr).pdf
19. HCN(7.3Torr)+N2+H2O(15.6Torr).pdf
20. HCN(7.3Torr)+N2+H2O(nika).pdf
21. HCN(14.2Torr)+N2+H2O(3.0Torr).pdf
22. HCN(14.2Torr)+N2+H2O(9.8Torr).pdf
23. HCN(14.2Torr)+N2+H2O(nikaTorr).pdf

After that, as described in the Appendix in the main paper, the R^2 -like indicator of the goodness of fit was calculated. The value was then plotted for each molecule separately (across all experiments). This is shown in files:

1. R_sq_hcn.pdf
2. R_sq_h2o.pdf
3. R_sq_co.pdf
4. R_sq_co2.pdf

The value for the indicator were then averaged to show the overall goodness of fit. The averaged result and the relevant discussion are in the Appendix of the main paper and are not shown here.

Measurement cells

Below, we show schematic drawings of the two irradiation cells which are part of the ELISE apparatus. The cells are interchangeable. Bot cells are made of borosilicate glass.

Figure S1: Irradiation cell for gas phase experiments.

The irradiation cell for gas phase experiments is roughly spherical in shape with four 1-inch-in-diameter cylindrical tubes welded to it. The cylinders are used for inlet and outlet of gas, entrance of the laser radiation and UV-Vis inspection window. Glass beads were placed on the bottom of the cell to scatter the passing radiation (otherwise, the bottom of the cell is would be damaged by the laser beam).

Figure S2: Irradiation cell for solid phase experiments.

The irradiation cell for solid phase experiments is cylindrical. The upper part is similar in design to the cell for the gas phase irradiation. The lower part contains a sample holder on which the solid sample can be placed. Underneath is a rotary shaft with a stepper motor nested in a glass tube. The glass tube is connected to the cell with a vacuum-tight joint. Both parts (the shaft and the sample holder) contain a magnet. The rotation of the stepper motor therefore rotates the sample and ensures that the laser does not ablate a single point in the sample. This is important a) because if the sample is inhomogeneous, ablation of more spots provides a more average result, and b) if the laser fired in one spot only, the sample would quickly be ablated away, and a hole would be created.

DCN and the reverse reaction

To prove the fact that the reaction of HCN decomposition is reversible, we performed experiments with D_2 as the source of deuterium and observed the formation of DCN in our experiment. A FTIR spectrum showing the band of DCN is shown in the main paper. Here in the Supplementary Information, we show

the relative abundances of HCN and DCN in the experiment. Figure S3 shows the relative abundance of HCN and Figure S4 shows the relative abundance of DCN.

Figure S3: The normalized relative abundance of HCN in the experiment.

Figure S4: The normalized relative abundance of DCN in the experiment.

The experiment at the beginning contained HCN and D₂. During the irradiation, the HCN is decomposed. In the first step, HCN presumably decomposes to H· and ·CN. At the same time, D₂ decomposes to two D· radicals. The D· and ·CN radicals may then react during the afterglow of the laser-generated plasma to form DCN. Figure S3 shows the relative decrease in the partial pressure of HCN during the experiment. Figure S4 then shows the formation of DCN. Data for both figures were normalized and show relative changes in the abundances. Interestingly, there is a moment when DCN reaches a maximum value and then decreases. At the start, the abundance of DCN increases as a lot of HCN is decomposed and no DCN is present. After some time, however, there is already enough DCN and small enough amount of HCN that the decomposition of DCN begins to dominate over its formation from HCN. The DCN FTIR spectrum in the main paper is the spectrum at the time of the maximum abundance of DCN in the sample.

Composition of the gas phase

In this section, we show some visualizations of the composition of the gas phase after 420 s of irradiation. The following plots were created from the experimental data and not the model. For each of the plots, we define Y_i , which is the relative amount of carbon locked in a specie i in the gas phase relative to other species in the gas phase. Y_i is defined as:

$$Y_i = \frac{p_i n_i}{\sum_i p_i n_i} \quad (11)$$

where p_i is the partial pressure of specie i and n_i is the number of carbon atoms in the molecule.

Figure S5 shows Y_{CO} with respect to the initial partial pressures of HCN and H_2O .

Figure S5: Y_{CO} with respect to the initial partial pressures of HCN and H_2O .

This figure shows that the gas phase in experiments with roughly equal amounts of HCN and H_2O is the highest. Higher initial amounts of H_2O relative to HCN lead to faster consumption of HCN and formation of CO and subsequently CO_2 . After 420 s of irradiation, then, the relative amount of CO in the gas phase decreases for experiments with high $p_{H_2O, ini} / p_{HCN, ini}$. At the same time, experiments with high initial content of HCN and little to no H_2O do not contain much CO either, mostly because there is little water for its production in the first place.

Figure S6 shows the same property, the Y_{CO_2} for CO_2 .

Figure S6: Y_{CO_2} with respect to the initial partial pressures of HCN and H_2O .

This figure shows the relative amount of CO_2 in the gas phase after 420 s of irradiation and clearly, the amounts are much lower than in the case of CO , with the exception of experiments with very little HCN at the beginning and relatively higher amounts of H_2O . Notably, in experiments with little to no H_2O , little to no CO_2 is formed. Even though CO is present in these experiments (some residual water is always present in the experiment), it seems to be so little that it is consumed for the formation of CO and none is left for the formation of CO_2 .

Figure S7 shows the same property, the $Y_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_2}$ for C_2H_2 .

Figure S7: $Y_{C_2H_2}$ with respect to the initial partial pressures of HCN and H_2O .

This figure shows the relative amount of carbon in the gas phase locked in acetylene. The formation of acetylene was observed only in three experiments. In these experiments, almost no water was initially present and the amounts of HCN were the highest of all the experiments. It can be expected that if even higher partial pressures of HCN were used, more acetylene could be formed. The actual observed amounts of acetylene were very small, but in the experiments where it was detected, little CO and CO_2 was formed as well. For this reason, in the one experiment with least water and most HCN at the beginning shows that up to 75% of the gas phase is acetylene. Most of the decomposition products of HCN in this experiment are solid products, which are not shown here, but are shown in the main paper.

UV-Vis spectra

As is described in the main paper, we observed UV-Vis spectra of the plasma produced in the gaseous mixtures. Unfortunately, the data were insufficient to reveal the reaction mechanism of the HCN decomposition. The main paper features an example spectrum from this measurement. Here we show in Figure S8 the relative abundance of the $\cdot CN$ in our experiments with different initial amounts of water, each after 420 s of irradiation.

Figure S8: Relative intensity of ·CN observed in our UV-Vis spectra.

It is clear from this figure that the abundance of ·CN decreases with the increasing amount of water in the system, pointing to the fact that ·OH radicals efficiently enhance the decomposition of HCN, as stated in the main paper.